

Synthesis of both kinetically and thermodynamically controlled diastereomeric pairs of bis-isoxazolidines from dibenzylideneacetone : Their reactivity and biological activity

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Abstract : Reactions of *C*-aryl-*N*-phenyl-nitrones with dibenzylideneacetone yielded pairs of diastereomeric bis-isoxazolidines in good to moderate yields. Both types of cycloadducts possessed identical regio- and stereo-selectivity. Molecular modeling studies revealed small difference in energy between the two isomers. Less stable isomer was converted to more stable one via partial cycloreversion followed by re-cycloaddition pathway. Zinc mediated acid catalyzed cycloreversion was observed for more stable diastereomer whereas less stable one yielded corresponding bis-1,3-aminoalcohols in similar condition. Some cycloadducts were screened for anticancer and antibacterial activity.

Keywords : Nitron, dibenzylideneacetone, bis-isoxazolidines, diastereomerism, cycloreversion, molecular modeling, anticancer, antibacterial.

Introduction

Dipolar cycloaddition reactions between nitrones and structurally diverse alkenes play key role for the straightforward construction of medicinally potent isoxazolidine skeleton¹. High degree control of regio- and stereo-selectivity could be achieved in both intra- and intermolecular pathways leading to this cyclic scaffold with the generation of upto three contiguous stereocenters^{2,3}. Presence of a labile N-O bond which can be easily cleaved under mild reducing conditions accounts for the common use of isoxazolidines as masked 1,3-aminoalcohol moieties⁴. Vulnerability of isoxazolidine rings and their inherent cycloreversible nature had been effectively manipulated for the syntheses of structurally diverse types of alkaloids^{5,6}. Cyclic compounds possessing cross-conjugated dienone systems viz. *p*-benzoquinone⁷ and dibenzylidene cycloalkanones⁸ etc. as dipolarophiles had yielded bis-cycloadducts involving both olefinic bonds.

Two pentaatomic heterocycles formed thereby were found to be in same or different steric dispositions with respect to each other around the plane of the rings.

Diarylideneacetones had been subjected to cycloaddition reactions with various dipolar species. Depending on the nature of the dipolarophile and the dipole concerned, involvement of either or both olefinic bonds and also of carbonyl function in the formation of cycloadducts were observed⁹. We had carried out reactions of dibenzylideneacetone with nitrones derived from various aromatic aldehydes and tried to explore the differences in stabilities vis-à-vis reactivities of the pairs of diastereomeric bis-isoxazolidines formed thereby from experimental observations and molecular modeling studies. Some of the cycloadducts exhibited interesting anticancer activity against human colon adenocarcinoma cell line (Colo-205) and antibacterial activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Shigella flexneri* by agar-well diffusion assay.

Results and discussion

Each of the *C*-aryl-*N*-phenyl-nitrones (**2a-g**, 2.5 eqv.) was reacted with dibenzylideneacetone (**1**, 1.0 eqv.) in dry toluene under N₂-blanket at 110 °C when respective diastereomeric bis-isoxazolidine derivatives **3a-g** and **4a-g** and mono-isoxazolidine derivative **5a-g** were formed (Scheme 1) as indicated from the ¹H NMR spectrum of each reaction mixture. Optimum time for each reaction and isolated yields of the products were given in Table 1.

tallographic analyses of two representative bis-isoxazolidines **3b** and **4b** established the differences in their stereo-structures and their crystal structures were shown as Figs. 1 and 2 respectively. The difference in steric dispositions of the two isoxazolidine rings in those two diastereomers was found to be similar with the pattern reported earlier^{9b}. X-Ray structure of **4b** indicated *enantiotopic* relationship between respective aliphatic H-atoms and in case of **3b**, these atoms were *homotopic*.

Scheme 1. Cycloaddition between different substituted nitrones and dibenzylideneacetone.

¹H and ¹³C NMR spectral analyses and mass spectrum for each of the isolated cycloadducts and ¹H NMR data for the products identifiable in reaction mixtures revealed close structural resemblances among the compounds belonging to each series **3a-g**, **4a-g** and **5a-g**. X-Ray crys-

It was found from the chemical shift values for aliphatic protons on C₃-, C₄- and C₅-carbons for **3a-g** and **4a-g** (Table 2) that for each respective pair of diastereoisomeric bis-isoxazolidines, C₃-H's of **3a-g** appeared downfield than the C₃-H's of **4a-g** while the C₅-H's for

Table 1. Cycloadducts from dibenzylideneacetone (**1**) and *C*-aryl-*N*-phenyl-nitrones (**2a-g**)

Sl. no.	Nitrones	Time (h)	Product yields (%)		
			3a-g	4a-g	5a-g
1.	2a	4.5	70	Trace ^{aa}	1
2.	2b	4	44	42	4
3.	2c	12	38	35	Trace ^{aa}
4.	2d	8	41	35	Trace ^{aa}
5.	2e	6	36	34	Trace ^{aa}
6.	2f	5.5	58	Trace ^{aa}	5
7.	2g	4	Trace ^{aa}	Trace ^{aa}	65

^{aa}Identified from ¹H NMR spectrum of reaction mixture.

Fig. 1. X-Ray crystallography of **3b**.

Fig. 2. X-Ray crystallography of **4b**.

3a-g resonated upfield against the C_5 -H's for **4a-g** and the extent of de-shielding for C_3 -H's for each respective pair was found to be comparable with the extent of shielding for C_5 -H's for the same pair. It was also noted that between each respective pair of bis-isoxazolidines **3a-g** and **4a-g**, the resonance signals for C_4 -H's for **3a-g** were discernible at upfield region than the C_4 -H's of **4a-g**. Thus ¹H NMR data were turned out to be useful tool to differentiate between these two types of diastereomeric bis-isoxazolidines.

The other important finding was the identical coupling constant values for protons on C_3 -, C_4 - and C_5 -carbons of isoxazolidine rings belonging to both series of diastereomers. These values indicated *trans* relationships¹⁰ between those vicinal protons, which were also identified from the X-ray structures of **3b** and **4b**, confirming both regio- and stereoselective nature of the reactions.

Table 3 summarized the chemical shift values for the aliphatic protons on C_3 -, C_4 - and C_5 -carbons and the respective α -olefinic protons of the mono-isoxazolidine derivatives **5a-g**. Resonance signals for corresponding β -olefinic protons merged with the signals for aromatic protons. Identical regio- and stereoselectivity in monoadducts with those observed in cases of bis-isoxazolidines were evident from the coupling constants values for vicinal aliphatic protons and X-ray structure of **5g** (Fig. 3).

Molecular modeling studies were undertaken to evaluate relative stability between two diastereomers **3b** and **4b**. The theoretical energies for these two compounds were calculated from DFT studies using B3LYP functional and 6-31G basis set. The structural input parameters for the two structures have been generated from the CIF file of their single crystal structures. The theoretical optimized structures for the two isomers have been given in Fig. 4.

DFT studies indicated that energy optimized structure of the diastereomer **3b** bearing two isoxazolidine rings sterically disposed on opposite sides with respect to central carbonyl function was 0.6827 kcal/mol more stable than isomer **4b** where two heterocyclic rings remained on same side.

The small energy difference between **3b** and **4b** was also indicated from experimental observations. Table 4

Table 2. Chemical shift (δ) values of the aliphatic protons attached to C₃, C₄ and C₅ for each compound belonging to series **3a-g** and **4a-g**

Product	C ₃ -H (d)			C ₅ -H (d)			C ₄ -H (dd)	
	δ (ppm)	$J_{3,4}$ (Hz)	Difference in δ values	δ (ppm)	$J_{4,5}$ (Hz)	Difference in δ values	δ (ppm)	Difference in δ values
3a	5.12	7.5	+0.38	4.71	9.6	-0.30	3.17	-0.07
4a^a	4.74	7.8		5.01	9.3		3.24	
3b	5.13	7.6	+0.41	4.67	9.3	-0.35	3.13	-0.06
4b	4.72	7.8		5.02	9.3		3.19	
3c	5.11	7.5	+0.39	4.67	9.3	-0.35	3.12	-0.08
4c	4.72	7.8		5.02	9.0		3.20	
3d	5.34	6.9	+0.50	4.58	9.0	-0.40	3.09	-0.10
4d	4.84	7.2		4.98	9.0		3.19	
3e	4.92	7.8	+0.23	4.80	9.0	-0.22	3.19	-0.06
4e	4.69	7.8		5.02	9.3		3.25	
3f	5.39	7.2	+0.42	4.62	9.6	-0.36	3.17	-0.09
4f^a	4.97	7.2		4.98	9.3		3.26	
3g^a	5.41	7.2	+0.46	4.62	9.6	-0.41	3.16	-0.12
4g^a	4.96	7.2		5.03	9.0		3.28	

^aData obtained from the ¹H NMR spectrum of reaction mixture.

Table 3. Chemical shift (δ) values for mono-isoxazolidine derivatives

Entry	Compd.	C ₃ -H, d (J in Hz)	C ₄ -H, dd	C ₅ -H, d (J in Hz)	α -Olefinic protons (J in Hz)
1	5a	5.98 (9.3)	4.18	5.13 (10.2)	6.39 (15.9)
2	5b	5.34 (7.2)	4.03	5.29 (9.3)	6.37 (15.0)
3	5c^a	5.36 (6.9)	4.18	5.30 (9.0)	6.50 (15.6)
4	5d^a	5.53 (6.8)	4.00	5.25 (9.3)	6.45 (16.1)
5	5e^a	5.15 (7.5)	4.10	5.30 (9.3)	6.40 (16.2)
6	5f	5.52 (6.6)	3.95	5.15 (9.3)	6.26 (16.2)
7	5g	5.63 (6.9)	4.03	5.25 (9.3)	6.37 (16.2)

^aData obtained from the ¹H NMR spectrum of the crude reaction mixture.

had depicted the results of heating these two compounds separately in dry toluene at 110 °C.

It had been found that **3b** experienced partial cycloreversion to **5b** and rate of the reversion process increased with time. When **4b** was heated, formation of both **3b** and **5b** occurred with gradual decline of starting material. However, complete cycloreversion of either bis-isoxazolidine derivative did not occur within stipulated period of heating. Though no isomerisation of **3b** to **4b** had taken place even after heating for 8 h, formation of

Fig. 3. X-Ray crystallography of **5g**.

3b from **4b** within 4 h of heating suggested a pathway involving partial cycloreversion of **4b** to **5b** followed by recycladdition. Thus **4b** could be identified as the kinetically controlled product and **3b** as thermodynamically stable product. Cycloreversion of nitrono cycloadduct followed by recycladdition was well documented for monoadducts^{5d}. However, interconversion between one bis-adduct to its diastereomer involving partial cycloreversion-recycladdition was not reported earlier.

Analyses of the ¹H NMR spectra of the reaction mix-

Fig. 4. Energy minimized structures of **3b** and **4b** obtained from DFT studies.

Table 4. Composition of mixtures after heating **3b** and **4b** separately in dry toluene at 110 °C

Entry	Compd.	Time (h)	Products identified (in ratio) ^a		
			3b	4b	5b
1	3b	4	3	-	2
2	3b	6	4	-	3
3	3b	8	1	-	1
4	4b	4	1	3	1
5	4b	6	1	3	2
6	4b	8	1	2	4

^aProduct ratio calculated from ¹H NMR spectrum of each reaction mixture.

tures of 1 h intervals during the cycloaddition reaction between dibenzylideneacetone **1** (1.0 eqv.) and C-(4-

chlorophenyl)-*N*-phenyl-nitrone **2b** (2.5 eqv.) revealed that yield of **3b** had progressively increased with time with respect to **4b** (Table 5). These data further indicated that isomer **4b** was kinetically formed product.

Table 5. Composition of mixtures at intervals during cycloaddition between **1** and **2b** in dry toluene at 110 °C

Time (h)	Products identified (in ratio) ^a	
	3b	4b
1	1	1.5
2	1	1.3
3	1	1.2
4	1.1	1

^aProduct ratio calculated from ¹H NMR spectrum of the reaction mixture.

Identical conclusion was arrived when the reaction between the dipolarophile **1** (1.0 eqv.) and nitrone **2b** (2.5 eqv.) was carried out at different temperatures. The results were presented in Table 6. Higher yields of **4b** were observed at lower temperatures though the role of solvents could not be ignored as in the case of acetonitrile (entry 1). At temperatures lower than 80 °C the reaction was very sluggish and those data were not reported here.

Table 6. Composition of mixtures during cycloaddition between **1** and **2b**

Entry	Solvent	Temp. (°C)	Time (h)	Conversion (%)	Products (in ratio) ^a	
					3b	4b
1	CH ₃ CN	80	2	90	1	1.2
2	Toluene	90	6	80	1	1.3
3	Toluene	110	4	100	1.1	1

^aProduct ratio calculated from ¹H NMR spectrum of the reaction mixture.

Reductive cleavage of N-O bonds present in isoxazolidine rings of the compound **3b** and **4b** were attempted separately with zinc and 50% acetic acid in dichloromethane at 60 °C for 2.5 h¹¹ (Scheme 2). While **4b** was smoothly transformed to the corresponding bis-1,3-aminoalcohols derivative **6**, **3b** experienced zinc-catalyzed cycloreversion in acidic medium furnishing dibenzylideneacetone **1**. Formation of **1** from **3b** was suggested to involve two steps. Initially two N-O bonds of bis-isoxazolidine rings of **3b** would be reduced to corresponding bis-1,3-aminoalcohols and the latter then underwent fragmentation to **1** in acidic medium. To corroborate this, the energy optimized structures for **6** and for postulated intermediate bis-1,3-aminoalcohols from

Scheme 2. Reductive cleavage of N-O bonds of 3b and 4b.

the reduction of 3b were calculated at AM1 level with Gaussian 03 software and presented in Fig. 5. It was found that structure 6 was 3.32 kcal/mol more stable than the postulated intermediate reduction product of 3b and the latter possessed *N*-phenyl groups in *anti* relationships with the hydroxyl groups leading to fragmentations to yield 1. In case of 6, those two functionalities were oriented *syn* to each other in both 1,3-aminoalcohol structures and existence of intramolecular H-bonding imparting stability to the compound were also indicated.

Screening of biological activity :

Preliminary screening of three pairs of diastereomers 3b and 4b, 3d and 4d and 3e and 4e for anticancer and antibacterial activities were undertaken. These pairs were chosen for the presence of three different types of substituents viz. chloro, cyano and methoxy groups respectively on *C*-aryl groups of the isoxazolidine rings in view of the differences in their electron donating ability. Testing of anticancer activity was carried out with human colon adenocarcinoma cell line, Colo-205 (ATCC) and the results were shown in Table 7. All the compounds showed more or less dose dependent cytotoxic activity and the highest activity was shown by the compounds 4b and 4e at a dose of 1×10^{-4} M. Both 4b and 4e possessed two isoxazolidine rings sterically disposed on the same side with respect to central carbonyl function. Incidentally, the cytotoxicity of indole based isoxazolidine system was also reported against two different colon cancer cell lines viz. HCT-15 and SW-620¹².

Postulated reduced product of 3b

$$E = 3.32 \text{ kcal/mol}$$

6

$$E = 0.000 \text{ kcal/mol}$$

Fig. 5. Energy minimized structures of postulated reduced product of 3b and of 6.

Same three pairs of bis-isoxazolidine derivatives were tested against ten clinical isolates of bacteria, both Gram-positive and Gram-negative, viz. *Bacillus subtilis*, *Micrococcus luteus*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *S. saprophyticus*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Klebsiella oxytoca*, *Moraxella catarrhalis*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Shigella flexneri*, collected from patients. Three ATCC strains, viz. *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Escherichia coli* and

Table 7. Cytotoxicity of the compounds **3b**, **4b**, **3d**, **4d**, **3e** and **4e** against Colo-205

Compd.	Tested	Inhibition of cell growth (%)
	dose (<i>M</i>)	
3b	1×10^{-6}	1.8
	1×10^{-5}	25.7
	1×10^{-4}	37.1
4b	1×10^{-6}	11.6
	1×10^{-5}	17.8
	1×10^{-4}	58.4
3d	1×10^{-6}	0.7
	1×10^{-5}	6.1
	1×10^{-4}	41.7
4d	1×10^{-6}	7.2
	1×10^{-5}	10.5
	1×10^{-4}	44.6
3e	1×10^{-6}	11.0
	1×10^{-5}	13.6
	1×10^{-4}	34.5
4e	1×10^{-6}	3.2
	1×10^{-5}	6.9
	1×10^{-4}	56.4
Doxorubicin ^a	1×10^{-6}	4.0
	1×10^{-5}	65.2

^aPositive control.

Klebsiella pneumoniae were also included in the study. The antibacterial activity was determined using agar well diffusion assay.

None of the Gram-positive bacteria responded positively to the compounds tested in this study at a dose range of 0.05–1.0 μ M. However, a mild response of a couple of Gram-negative strains, viz. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Shigella flexneri* were observed for the compounds **3b**, **4b**, **3e** and **4e** and the results were presented in Table 8. These results indicated that bis-isoxazolidines possessing electron donating 4-chloro and 4-methoxy groups on aromatic rings substituted on C₅-carbon of isoxazolidine rings showed promise for anti-cancer and antibacterial properties.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary tubes on Kofler block apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in KBr discs with a Perkin-Elmer RXI FT-IR spectrophotometer. NMR spectra (¹H and ¹³C) were

Table 8. Antibacterial activity of compounds **3b**, **4b**, **3d**, **4d**, **3e** and **4e** against clinical isolates of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Shigella flexneri* by agar-well diffusion assay

Compd. code	Diameter of inhibition zone (in mm) ^a					
	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>			<i>S. flexneri</i>		
	(1 × 10 ⁷ cfu/mL)			(1 × 10 ⁷ cfu/mL)		
Doses of tested compds. (μ M) →	0.05	0.5	1.0	0.05	0.5	1.0
3b	9	8	8	x	8	8
4b	10	9	9	x	x	10
3d	x	x	x	x	x	x
4d	x	x	x	x	x	x
3e	9	9	9	x	x	x
4e	8	9	9	x	x	x
Streptomycin (0.1 mg/mL)		15			x	
Gentamicin (0.1 mg/mL)		x				17

^aIncluding diameter of well (7 mm); x - No activity.

recorded in CDCl₃ solution in 5 mm BBO probe fitted with a pulse field gradient and working with Topspin 1.3 programme in a Bruker AV-300 Supercon NMR spectrometer (chemical shifts in δ ppm and *J* in Hz). Mass spectrometry was performed on a Qtof Micro YA 263 mass spectrometer operating at an ionization potential 8.96 eV. X-Ray crystallographic data were taken on a Bruker Smart Apex 2 diffractometer equipped with a CCD area detector with graphite monochromatized Mo K α radiation. Both column chromatography and TLC were done with silica gel. A CO₂-incubator from NuAire, USA and ELISA reader (model 680) from BIO-RAD, USA, were used in the cytotoxicity assay. Colo-205 (ATCC) cell line was procured from LGC Promochem India Ltd., Bangalore. Bacterial cultures were maintained in a bacteriological incubator at 37 °C. Nutrient agar, Muller Hinton broth, and RPMI-1640 medium were procured from Himedia, Mumbai.

General :

Typical cycloaddition reaction procedure :

Nitrones were prepared by the standard procedure. To the hot solution of nitrone (15 mmol) in dry toluene (30 mL), a solution of dibenzylideneacetone [6 mmol in dry toluene (20 mL)] was added and heating at 110 °C was continued under nitrogen atmosphere. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC. After completion

of the reaction, toluene was removed under reduced pressure using an Eyela rotary evaporator. Concentrated reaction mixture was subjected to column chromatography using silica gel (100–200 mesh, Merck) and eluted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80 °C) and ethyl acetate mixture of increasing polarities

Reduction of the cycloadducts (3b and 4b) :

To separate solutions of bis-isoxazolidine **3b** (125 mg, 0.179 mmol) and **4b** (125 mg, 0.179 mmol) in dichloromethane (7 mL) and 50% aqueous acetic acid (10 mL), zinc dust (82 mg, 1.255 mmol) was added. The solution was heated to 60 °C for 2.5 h and then cooled to room temperature. The reaction mixture was filtered and the filtrate extracted with dichloromethane three times (10 mL × 3). The mixed organic layer was washed three times (10 mL × 3) with water, once with very dilute ammonia solution and finally thrice with water. The dichloromethane layer was dried over sodium sulphate and concentrated to give the cycloreversed product **1** from **3b** and the aminoalcohol **6** from **4b** respectively.

Experiments on biological activity :

(a) Preparation of test solutions for biological assay :

Drug solutions were prepared as 5 mM stocks by dissolving in sterile dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO; Analytical grade) aseptically, and diluted with either the culture medium (for cytotoxicity assay), or DMSO (antibacterial assay) to get the desired concentrations of the test solutions. The final concentration of DMSO in the culture was adjusted to 0.1% (v/v).

(b) Cytotoxicity against colon cancer cell line Colo-205 :

Human colon adenocarcinoma cell line Colo-205 (ATCC) was cultured in RPMI-1640 medium, supplemented with 10% heat-inactivated Fetal Bovine Serum and antibiotics (streptomycin 200 µg/mL, gentamicin 200 µg/mL, and penicillin 100 units/mL) at 37 °C in humidified 5% CO₂ atmosphere. The medium was removed after 24 h of plating of the cells, and replaced with fresh medium containing either drugs at different concentrations, or DMSO as the vehicle control. Antiproliferative effect of the compounds **3b**, **4b**, **3d**, **4d**, **3e**, **4e** were investigated by MTT [3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide] dye uptake method¹³. Briefly, trypsinized cells (10⁴/well) were incubated over-

night in 96-well plate at 37 °C for attachment. Cells were then treated with drugs at the concentrations of 1 × 10⁻⁶, 1 × 10⁻⁵ and 1 × 10⁻⁴ M in a final volume of 200 µL, leaving the 'control' wells as 'untreated'. Doxorubicin served as positive control for each experiment. The culture plate was incubated for 24 h, followed by addition of MTT (0.5 mg/mL, in PBS), to each well. The plates were then further incubated for 3 h at 37 °C. Thereafter, the cell pellet was re-suspended in DMSO (100 µL) and absorbance was measured at 570 nm in an ELISA reader. The percentage of growth inhibition was calculated with respect to untreated control using the following formula : [(O.D. of untreated control - O.D. of the respective treated set)/O.D. of untreated control × 100].

(c) Agar well diffusion method :

The antibacterial activity was determined using agar well diffusion assay¹⁴. The compounds were dissolved in DMSO and tested at the concentration range of 0.05–1.0 µM/well for their antibacterial activities. The bacterial culture in Muller Hinton broth was adjusted to the final inoculum density of 1 × 10⁷ cfu/mL (by 0.5 McFarland standard), and allowed to dry in culture plates. After solidification, wells were made with a sterile borer in the pre-inoculated MHA plates, and 100 µL each of the test solutions were dispensed in the wells. The diameter of the inhibition zone was measured after 24 h incubation at 37 °C. Antimicrobial activity was expressed as the diameter of inhibition zone produced by a tested compound.

Spectroscopic data of the cycloadducts :

(±)-rel-Bis(3R,4S,5S)-2,3,5-triphenylisoxazolidin-4-yl)methanone (3a) :

White crystalline solid; yield 913 mg (70%), crystallization from chloroform-petroleum ether, m.p. 151–152 °C; IR (KBr) : 3032, 1709, 1594, 1487, 1002 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 3.17 (1H, dd, *J* 9.6, 7.5 Hz), 4.71 (1H, d, *J* 9.6 Hz), 5.12 (1H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz), 6.68 (2H, d, *J* 7.3 Hz), 6.86 (2H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 6.92 (1H, t, *J* 7.3 Hz), 7.09–7.31 (10H, m); ¹³C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 72.33 (CH), 74.06 (CH), 83.11 (CH), 114.14 (2 × CH), 121.83 (CH), 126.31 (2 × CH), 127.06 (2 × CH), 127.83 (1 × CH), 128.89 (2 × CH), 128.94 (3 × CH), 129.05 (2 × CH), 135.12 (C), 140.76 (C), 151.42 (C), 201.39 (C); HRMS calcd. for C₄₃H₃₆N₂O₃Na (M+Na)⁺ : 651.2624, found : 651.2606.

Meso-((3*R*, 4*S*, 5*S*)-2, 3, 5-triphenylisoxazolidin-4-yl)(3*S*, 4*R*, 5*R*)-2, 3, 5-triphenylisoxazolidin-4-yl)methanone (crude reaction product) (**4a**) :

¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 3.24 (1H, dd, *J* 9.3, 7.8 Hz), 4.74 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 5.01 (1H, d, *J* 9.3 Hz), 6.80–7.40 (15H, m). Spectra indicated presence of **3a** which could not be separated.

(*E*)-3-Phenyl-1-((3*R*, 4*S*, 5*S*)-2, 3, 5-triphenylisoxazolidin-4-yl)prop-2-en-1-one (**5a**) :

Yellow powder, yield 8 mg (1%), m.p. 155–157 °C; IR (KBr) : 2928, 1598, 1118 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 4.18 (1H, dd, *J* 10.2, 9.3 Hz), 5.13 (1H, d, *J* 10.2 Hz), 5.98 (1H, d, *J* 9.3 Hz), 6.39 (1H, d, *J* 15.9 Hz), 6.96 (1H, t, *J* 6.8 Hz), 7.06 (2H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz), 7.20–7.40 (14H, m), 7.47 (2H, d, *J* 7.3 Hz), 7.53 (2H, d, *J* 7.3 Hz); HRMS calcd. for C₃₀H₂₅NO₂Na (M+Na)⁺ : 454.1783, found : 454.1837.

(±)-*rel*-Bis((3*R*, 4*S*, 5*S*)-3-(4-chlorophenyl)-2, 5-diphenylisoxazolidin-4-yl)methanone (**3b**) :

White crystalline solid, yield 617 mg (44%), m.p. 167–168 °C; IR (KBr) : 3040, 1708, 1594, 1487, 1007, 831, 756, 692 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 3.13 (1H, dd, *J* 9.3, 7.6 Hz), 4.67 (1H, d, *J* 9.3 Hz), 5.13 (1H, d, *J* 7.6 Hz), 6.72 (2H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz), 6.85 (2H, d, *J* 7.7 Hz), 6.96 (1H, t, *J* 7.4 Hz), 7.11–7.37 (9H, m); ¹³C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 71.60 (CH), 73.97 (CH), 83.38 (CH), 114.04 (2 × CH), 122.07 (CH), 127.06 (2 × CH), 127.64 (2 × CH), 129.00 (2 × CH), 129.04 (2 × CH), 129.22 (2 × CH), 129.40 (CH), 133.69 (C), 134.52 (C), 139.33 (C), 151.17 (C), 200.93 (C); HRMS calcd. for C₄₃H₃₅Cl₂N₂O₃ (MH⁺) : 697.2025 (for ³⁵Cl), found : 697.2015. The crystal structure had been deposited at the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre and been allocated the deposition number CCDC 868505.

Meso-((3*R*, 4*S*, 5*S*)-3-(4-chlorophenyl)-2, 5-diphenylisoxazolidin-4-yl)(3*S*, 4*R*, 5*R*)-3-(4-chlorophenyl)-2, 5-diphenylisoxazolidin-4-yl)methanone (**4b**) :

White crystalline solid, yield 590 mg (42%), m.p. 162–164 °C; IR (KBr) : 3035, 1710, 1595, 1488, 1009, 833, 755, 693 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 3.19 (1H, dd, *J* 9.3, 7.8 Hz), 4.72 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 5.02 (1H, d, *J* 9.3 Hz), 6.84 (2H, d, *J* 7.7 Hz), 6.90 (2H, d, *J* 7.3 Hz), 6.97 (1H, t, *J* 7.3 Hz), 7.03 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 7.20–7.37 (7H, m); ¹³C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl₃) :

δ 72.72 (CH), 73.93 (CH), 82.18 (CH), 114.42 (2 × CH), 122.39 (CH), 126.64 (2 × CH), 127.94 (2 × CH), 128.90 (2 × CH), 129.03 (3 × CH), 129.33 (2 × CH), 134.02 (C), 135.45 (C), 139.04 (C), 150.91 (C), 201.63 (C); HRMS calcd. for C₄₃H₃₄Cl₂N₂O₃Na (M+Na)⁺ : 719.1844 (for ³⁵Cl), found : 719.1834. The following crystal structure had been deposited at the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre and been allocated the deposition number CCDC 875588.

(*E*)-1-((3*R*, 4*S*, 5*S*)-3-(4-chlorophenyl)-2, 5-diphenylisoxazolidin-4-yl)-3-phenylprop-2-en-1-one (**5b**) :

Yellow solid, yield 56 mg (4%), m.p. 155–157 °C; IR (KBr) : 2923, 2855, 1724, 1654, 1596, 1455, 1087, 827, 754, 692 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 4.03 (1H, dd, *J* 9.3, 7.2 Hz), 5.29 (1H, d, *J* 9.3 Hz), 5.34 (1H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz), 6.37 (1H, d, *J* 15.0 Hz), 6.97–7.55 (20H, m); ¹³C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 68.62 (CH), 70.52 (CH), 80.86 (CH), 117.39 (2 × CH), 123.29 (CH), 125.54 (CH), 127.23 (2 × CH), 128.19 (2 × CH), 128.42 (2 × CH), 128.56 (CH), 128.69 (2 × CH), 128.79 (2 × CH), 129.28 (2 × CH), 129.57 (2 × CH), 130.53 (CH), 133.73 (C), 134.16 (C), 135.06 (C), 139.43 (C), 142.68 (CH), 149.28 (C), 195.15 (C); HRMS calcd. for C₃₀H₂₄ClNO₂Na (M+Na)⁺ : 488.1394 (for ³⁵Cl), found : 488.1403.

(±)-*rel*-Bis((3*R*, 4*S*, 5*S*)-3-(4-bromophenyl)-2, 5-diphenylisoxazolidin-4-yl)methanone (**3c**) :

White crystalline solid, yield 490 mg (35%), m.p. 160–162 °C; IR (KBr) : 3039, 1708, 1593, 1486, 1006, 827, 756, 693 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 3.12 (1H, dd, *J* 9.3, 7.5 Hz), 4.67 (1H, d, *J* 9.3 Hz), 5.11 (1H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz), 6.72 (2H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 6.85 (2H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 6.96 (1H, t, *J* 7.4 Hz), 7.06 (2H, d, *J* 7.3 Hz), 7.15–7.17 (4H, m), 7.34 (1H, t, *J* 7.3 Hz), 7.43 (2H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz); ¹³C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 71.67 (CH), 73.94 (CH), 83.41 (CH), 114.07 (2 × CH), 121.78 (C), 122.09 (CH), 127.07 (2 × CH), 127.99 (2 × CH), 129.02 (CH), 129.05 (3 × CH), 129.41 (CH), 132.20 (2 × CH), 134.53 (C), 139.89 (C), 151.16 (C), 200.93 (C); HRMS calcd. for C₄₃H₃₄Br₂N₂O₃Na (M+Na)⁺ : 809.0814 (for ⁸¹Br), found : 809.0862.

Meso-((3*R*, 4*S*, 5*S*)-3-(4-bromophenyl)-2, 5-diphenylisoxazolidin-4-yl)(3*S*, 4*R*, 5*R*)-3-(4-bromophenyl)-2, 5-diphenylisoxazolidin-4-yl)methanone (**4c**) :

White crystalline solid, yield 534 mg (38%), m.p.

156–158 °C; IR (KBr) : 3034, 1710, 1594, 1486, 1008, 831, 754, 693 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 3.20 (1H, dd, *J* 9.0, 7.8 Hz), 4.72 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 5.02 (1H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz), 6.84 (2H, d, *J* 7.9 Hz), 6.91 (2H, d, *J* 7.3 Hz), 6.97 (3H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 7.23 (4H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz), 7.34 (1H, t, *J* 7.4 Hz), 7.45 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz); ¹³C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 72.75 (CH), 73.87 (CH), 82.17 (CH), 114.42 (2 × CH), 122.08 (C), 122.39 (CH), 126.63 (2 × CH), 128.24 (2 × CH), 128.89 (2 × CH), 129.03 (3 × CH), 132.29 (2 × CH), 135.42 (C), 139.54 (C), 150.86 (C), 201.59 (C); HRMS calcd. for C₄₃H₃₅Br₂N₂O₃ (MH⁺) : 789.1015 (for ⁸¹Br), found : 789.1367.

(*E*)-1-((3*R*, 4*S*, 5*S*)-3-(4-Bromophenyl)-2,5-diphenylisoxazolidin-4-yl)-3-phenylprop-2-en-1-one (crude reaction product) (**5c**) :

Crude reaction mixture; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 4.18 (1H, dd, *J* 9.00, 6.9 Hz), 5.30 (1H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz), 5.36 (1H, d, *J* 6.9 Hz), 6.50 (1H, d, *J* 15.6 Hz). Spectra indicated presence of **3c**, **4c** along with **5c** which could not be separated.

(±)-*rel*-4,4'-(3*R*,3'*R*,4*S*,4'*S*,5*S*,5'*S*)-4,4'-Carbonylbis(2,5-diphenylisoxazolidine-4,3-diyl)dibenzonitrile (**3d**) :

White crystalline solid, yield 505 mg (36%), m.p. 162–164 °C; IR (KBr) : 3039, 1704, 1598, 1490, 1006, 839, 758, 693 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 3.09 (1H, dd, *J* 9.0, 7.5 Hz), 4.58 (1H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz), 5.34 (1H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz), 6.60 (2H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz), 6.85 (2H, d, *J* 7.9 Hz), 7.00 (1H, t, *J* 7.3 Hz), 7.14 (2H, t, *J* 7.6 Hz), 7.24–7.36 (5H, m), 7.64 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz); ¹³C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 71.22 (CH), 73.59 (CH), 83.78 (CH), 111.91 (C), 113.88 (2 × CH), 122.36 (CH), 122.36 (C), 126.98 (2 × CH), 127.07 (2 × CH), 129.10 (2 × CH), 129.21 (2 × CH), 129.76 (CH), 132.88 (2 × CH), 133.76 (C), 146.27 (C), 150.72 (C), 200.23 (C); HRMS calcd. for C₄₅H₃₄N₄O₃Na (M+Na)⁺ : 701.2529, found : 701.2491.

Meso-4-((3*R*, 4*S*, 5*S*)-4-((3*S*, 4*R*, 5*R*)-3-(4-cyanophenyl)-2,5-diphenylisoxazolidine-4-carbonyl)-2,5-diphenylisoxazolidine-3-yl)benzonitrile (**4d**) :

White crystalline solid, yield 590 mg (42.6%), m.p. 158–160 °C; IR (KBr) : 3034, 1710, 1596, 1487, 1004, 841, 756, 692 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 3.19 (1H, dd, *J* 7.2, 9.0 Hz), 4.84 (1H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz),

4.98 (1H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz), 6.79 (2H, d, *J* 7.9 Hz), 6.84 (2H, d, *J* 7.4 Hz), 6.99 (1H, t, *J* 7.4 Hz), 7.15–7.28 (6H, m), 7.33 (1H, t, *J* 7.4 Hz), 7.56 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz); ¹³C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 72.55 (CH), 73.78 (CH), 82.41 (CH), 112.27 (C), 114.28 (2 × CH), 122.75 (CH), 122.75 (C), 126.59 (2 × CH), 127.16 (2 × CH), 129.05 (2 × CH), 129.23 (CH), 129.31 (2 × CH), 132.94 (2 × CH), 133.20 (C), 146.02 (C), 162.34 (C), 201.20 (C); HRMS calcd. for C₄₅H₃₄N₄O₃Na (M+Na)⁺ : 701.2529, found : 701.2557.

4-((3*R*, 4*S*, 5*S*)-4-Cinnamoyl-2,5-diphenylisoxazolidine-3-yl)benzonitrile (crude reaction product) (**5d**) :

Crude reaction mixture; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 4.00 (1H, dd, *J* 9.3, 6.8 Hz), 5.25 (1H, d, *J* 9.3 Hz), 5.53 (1H, d, *J* 6.8 Hz), 6.45 (1H, d, *J* 16.1 Hz). Spectra indicated presence of **3d**, **4d** along with **5d** which could not be separated.

(±)-*rel*-Bis((3*R*, 4*S*, 5*S*)-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-2,5-diphenylisoxazolidin-4-yl)methanone (**3e**) :

White crystalline solid, yield 510 mg (36%), m.p. 138–140 °C; IR (KBr) : 3032, 1709, 1598, 1502, 1242, 1002, 756, 691 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 3.19 (1H, dd, *J* 9.0, 7.8 Hz), 3.81 (3H, s), 4.80 (1H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz), 4.92 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 6.78 (3H, t, *J* 8.7 Hz), 6.82 (3H, t, *J* 8.7 Hz), 6.90 (1H, t, *J* 7.4 Hz), 7.02 (2H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz), 7.17 (4H, t, *J* 7.1 Hz), 7.30 (1H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz); ¹³C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 55.35 (CH₃), 72.30 (CH), 73.95 (CH), 82.73 (CH), 114.37 (4 × CH), 121.89 (CH), 126.99 (2 × CH), 127.60 (2 × CH), 128.85 (3 × CH), 128.96 (2 × CH), 132.43 (C), 135.63 (C), 151.38 (C), 159.25 (C), 201.89 (C); HRMS calcd. for C₄₅H₄₁N₂O₅ (MH)⁺ : 689.3016, found : 689.3025.

Meso-((3*R*, 4*S*, 5*S*)-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-2,5-diphenylisoxazolidin-4-yl)((3*S*, 4*R*, 5*R*)-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-2,5-diphenylisoxazolidin-4-yl)methanone (**4e**) :

Pale white crystalline solid, yield 480 mg (34%), m.p. 134–136 °C; IR (KBr) : 3023, 1706, 1600, 1503, 1249, 1020, 832, 756, 692 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 3.25 (1H, dd, *J* 9.1, 8.0 Hz), 3.85 (3H, s), 4.69 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 5.02 (1H, d, *J* 9.1 Hz), 6.83 (4H, t, *J* 7.3 Hz), 6.92 (3H, d, *J* 7.3 Hz), 7.0 (2H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz), 7.18 (4H, t, *J* 7.3 Hz), 7.30 (1H, d, *J* 7.3 Hz); ¹³C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 55.38 (CH₃), 73.02 (CH), 73.81

(CH), 82.09 (CH), 114.44 (2 × CH), 114.49 (2 × CH), 122.01 (CH), 126.72 (2 × CH), 127.92 (2 × CH), 128.76 (3 × CH), 128.85 (2 × CH), 132.38 (C), 135.84 (C), 151.36 (C), 159.40 (C), 202.29 (C); HRMS calcd. for C₄₅H₄₀N₂O₅Na (M+Na)⁺ : 711.2835, found : 711.2872.

(*E*)-1-((3*R*, 4*S*, 5*S*)-3-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-2,5-diphenylisoxazolidin-4-yl)-3-phenylprop-2-en-1-one (crude reaction product) (**5e**) :

Crude reaction mixture; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 4.10 (1H, dd, *J* 9.3, 7.5 Hz), 5.15 (1H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz), 5.30 (1H, d, *J* 9.3 Hz), 6.40 (1H, d, *J* 16.2 Hz). Spectra indicated presence of **3e**, **4e** along with **5e** which could not be separated.

(±)-*rel*-Bis((3*R*, 4*S*, 5*S*)-3-(3-nitrophenyl)-2,5-diphenylisoxazolidin-4-yl)methanone (**3f**) :

Light yellow crystalline solid, yield 810 mg (58%), m.p. 178–180 °C; IR (KBr) : 3030, 1710, 1596, 1525, 1348, 754, 691 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 3.17 (1H, dd, *J* 9.6, 7.2 Hz), 4.62 (1H, d, *J* 9.6 Hz), 5.39 (1H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz), 6.64 (2H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz), 6.85 (2H, d, *J* 7.7 Hz), 6.98 (1H, t, *J* 7.4 Hz), 7.10 (2H, t, *J* 7.6 Hz), 7.20–7.30 (3H, m), 7.47–7.57 (2H, m), 8.14–8.19 (2H, m); ¹³C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 70.96 (CH), 73.62 (CH), 83.88 (CH), 113.90 (2 × CH), 121.35 (CH), 122.43 (CH), 122.95 (CH), 127.07 (2 × CH), 129.02 (2 × CH), 129.19 (2 × CH), 129.82 (CH), 130.06 (CH), 132.32 (CH), 133.59 (C), 143.22 (C), 148.97 (C), 150.72 (C), 200.02 (C); HRMS calcd. for C₄₃H₃₄N₄O₇Na (M+Na)⁺ : 741.2325, found : 741.2309.

Meso-((3*R*, 4*S*, 5*S*)-3-(3-nitrophenyl)-2,5-diphenylisoxazolidin-4-yl)((3*S*, 4*R*, 5*R*)-3-(3-nitrophenyl)-2,5-diphenylisoxazolidin-4-yl)methanone (crude reaction product) (**4f**) :

Crude reaction mixture; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 3.26 (1H, dd, *J* 9.3, 7.2 Hz), 4.97 (1H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz), 4.98 (1H, d, *J* 9.3 Hz), 6.80–8.20 (m). Spectra indicated presence of **3f** and **5f** along with **4f** which could not be separated in pure form.

(*E*)-1-((3*R*, 4*S*, 5*S*)-3-(3-Nitrophenyl)-2,5-diphenylisoxazolidin-4-yl)-3-phenylprop-2-en-1-one (**5f**) :

Yellow semi solid, yield 70 mg (5%); IR (KBr) : 2963, 1601, 1261, 1025, 801 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 3.95 (1H, dd, *J* 9.3, 6.6 Hz), 5.15 (1H, d, *J* 9.3 Hz), 5.52 (1H, d, *J* 6.6 Hz), 6.26 (1H, d, *J* 16.2 Hz), 6.88

(1H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz), 6.96 (2H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 7.05–7.37 (13H, m), 7.47 (1H, t, *J* 8.0 Hz), 7.80 (1H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz), 8.04 (1H, d, *J* 7.5 Hz), 8.39 (1H, s); ¹³C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 72.30 (CH), 72.77 (CH), 84.24 (CH), 114.06 (2 × CH), 121.39 (CH), 122.15 (CH), 122.68 (CH), 124.50 (CH), 127.11 (2 × CH), 128.37 (2 × CH), 128.63 (2 × CH), 128.81 (CH), 128.94 (2 × CH), 129.15 (CH), 129.21 (CH), 129.99 (CH), 131.06 (CH), 132.50 (CH), 133.53 (C), 135.95 (C), 144.28 (C), 145.44 (CH), 148.75 (C), 150.94 (C), 193.97 (C); HRMS calcd. for C₃₀H₂₄N₂O₄Na (M+Na)⁺ : 499.1634, found : 499.1629.

(±)-*rel*-Bis((3*R*, 4*S*, 5*S*)-3-(4-nitrophenyl)-2,5-diphenylisoxazolidin-4-yl)methanone (crude reaction product) (**3g**) :

Crude reaction mixture; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 3.16 (1H, dd, *J* 9.6, 7.2 Hz), 4.62 (1H, d, *J* 9.6 Hz), 5.41 (1H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz). Spectra indicated presence of **4g**, **5g** along with **3g** which could not be separated.

Meso-((3*R*, 4*S*, 5*S*)-3-(4-nitrophenyl)-2,5-diphenylisoxazolidin-4-yl)((3*S*, 4*R*, 5*R*)-3-(4-nitrophenyl)-2,5-diphenylisoxazolidin-4-yl)methanone (crude reaction product) (**4g**) :

Crude reaction mixture; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 3.28 (1H, dd, *J* 7.2, 9.0 Hz), 4.96 (1H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz), 5.03 (1H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz). Spectra indicated presence of **3g**, **5g** along with **4g** which could not be separated.

(*E*)-1-((3*R*, 4*S*, 5*S*)-3-(4-Nitrophenyl)-1,5-diphenylisoxazolidin-4-yl)-3-phenylprop-2-en-1-one (**5g**) :

Yellow crystalline solid, yield 910 mg (65%), m.p. 94–96 °C; IR (KBr) : 3057, 1660, 1598, 1514, 1339, 754, 690 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 4.03 (1H, dd, *J* 9.3, 6.9 Hz), 5.25 (1H, d, *J* 9.3 Hz), 5.63 (1H, d, *J* 6.9 Hz), 6.37 (1H, d, *J* 16.2 Hz), 6.90–7.07 (3H, m), 7.16–7.21 (3H, m), 7.26–7.37 (4H, m), 7.40–7.49 (6H, m), 7.78 (2H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz), 8.27 (2H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz); ¹³C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 72.46 (CH), 72.86 (CH), 84.32 (CH), 114.09 (2 × CH), 122.25 (CH), 124.33 (2 × CH), 124.54 (C), 127.18 (2 × CH), 127.28 (2 × CH), 128.46 (2 × CH), 128.93 (2 × CH), 129.04 (2 × CH), 129.25 (2 × CH), 129.34 (CH), 131.20 (CH), 133.58 (CH), 136.00 (CH), 145.60 (C), 147.54 (C), 149.42 (C), 150.95 (C), 194.04 (C); HRMS calcd. for C₃₀H₂₄N₂O₄Na (M+Na)⁺ : 499.1634, found : 499.1629.

The crystal structure had been deposited at the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre and been allocated the deposition number CCDC 873494.

(2*S*, 3*R*, 5*S*, 6*R*)-2, 6-Bis(4-chlorophenyl)-3-((*R*)-hydroxy(phenyl)methyl)-5((*S*)-hydroxy(phenyl)methyl)-2, 6-bis(phenylamino)heptan-4-one (6) :

White crystalline solid, yield 88 mg (70.4%), m.p. 66–68 °C; IR (KBr) : 3490, 3396, 1709, 1602, 1502, 1091, 749, 698 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 3.47 (1H, dd, *J* 5.1, 5.4 Hz), 4.88 (1H, d, *J* 5.1 Hz), 4.98 (1H, d, *J* 5.4 Hz), 6.30 (2H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 6.69 (1H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz), 6.83 (2H, d, *J* 8.7 Hz), 6.98 (4H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 7.08 (2H, t, *J* 8.1 Hz), 7.18 (3H, t, *J* 4 Hz); ¹³C NMR (75.5 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 56.52 (CH), 62.72 (CH), 72.93 (CH), 114.04 (2 × CH), 118.38 (CH), 125.95 (2 × CH), 127.66 (CH), 128.29 (2 × CH), 128.42 (2 × CH), 128.84 (2 × CH), 129.25 (2 × CH), 132.75 (C), 138.43 (C), 140.88 (C), 145.73 (C), 210.12 (C); HRMS calcd. for C₄₃H₃₈Cl₂N₂O₃Na (M+Na)⁺ : 723.2157 (for ³⁵Cl), found : 723.2154.

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References

- For recent reviews on nitrone cycloadditions : (a) I. A. Grigor'ev, "Nitrile Oxides, Nitrones and Nitronates in Organic Synthesis", ed. H. Feuer, Wiley Interscience, 2008, p. 129; (b) T. B. Nguyen, A. Martel, C. Gaulon-Nourry, R. Dhal and G. Dujardin, *Org. Prep. Proc. Int.*, 2012, **44**, 1; (c) B. A. Moosa and S. A. Ali, *Arkivoc*, 2010, 132.
- For reviews on asymmetric 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions : (a) K. V. Gothelf and K. A. Jorgensen, "Synthetic Applications of 1,3-Dipolar Cycloaddition Chemistry towards Heterocycles and Natural Products", eds. A. Padwa and W. H. Pearson, John Wiley and Sons, New York, 2002, p. 817; (b) H. M. I. Osborn, N. Gammell and L. M. Harwood, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 2002, 2419; (c) H. Pellissier, *Tetrahedron*, 2007, **63**, 3235; (d) Y. Xing and N. X. Wang, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2012, **256**, 938; (e) J. Revuelta, S. Cicchi, A. Goti and A. Brandi, *Synthesis*, 2007, 485; (f) M. Kissane and A. R. Maguire, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2010, **39**, 845; (g) L. M. Stanley and M. P. Sibi, *Chem. Rev.*, 2008, **108**, 2887.
- (a) C. Palomo, M. Oiarbide, E. Arceo, J. M. Garcia, R. Lopez, A. Gonzalez and A. Linden, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2005, **44**, 6187; (b) R. C. Bernotas, L. Sing and D. Friedrich, *Synthesis*, 2005, 465; (c) A. Alsbaiee and S. A. Ali, *Tetrahedron*, 2008, **64**, 6635; (d) W. S. Jen, J. J. M. Wiener and D. W. C. Macmillan, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **122**, 9874; (e) K.-C. Lim, Y.-T. Hong and S. Kim, *Adv. Syn. Catal.*, 2008, **350**, 380; (f) T. Hashimoto, M. Omote, T. Kano and K. Maruoka, *Org. Lett.*, 2007, 4805; (g) D. Chen, Z. Wang, J. Li, Z. Yang, L. Lin, X. Liu and X. Feng, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2011, **17**, 5226; (h) W. Du, Y.-K. Liu, L. Yue and Y.-C. Chen, *Synlett*, 2008, 2997; (i) X. Wang, X. Xu, P. Y. Zavaliy and M. P. Doyle, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2011, **133**, 16402; (j) X. Ding, K. Taniguchi, Y. Hamamoto, K. Sada, S. Fujinami, Y. Ukaji and K. Inomata, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 2006, **79**, 1069; (k) Y. Jun, L. L. Xue, L. Bo and Y. Yanchao, *J. Chem. Res.*, 2012, **36**, 131; (l) A. Sakakura, M. Hori, M. Fushimi and K. Ishihara, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2010, **132**, 15550; (m) X. Wu, R. Na, H. Liu, J. Liu, M. Wang, J. Zhong and H. Guo, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2012, **53**, 342; (n) A. G. Larina, A. V. Stepakov, V. M. Boitsov, A. P. Molchanov, V. V. Gurzhiy, G. L. Starova and A. N. Lykholay, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2011, **52**, 5777.
- (a) K. P. Kaliappan, P. Das and N. Kumar, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2005, **46**, 3037; (b) D. A. Evans, H. J. Song and K. R. Fandrick, *Org. Lett.*, 2006, **8**, 3351; (c) T. Shimizu, M. Ishizaki and N. Nitada, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 2002, **50**, 908; (d) M. Shindo, K. Ohtsuki and K. Shishido, *Tetrahedron : Asymmetry*, 2005, **16**, 2821; (e) H. K. Zhang, W. H. Chan, W. M. Lee, P. F. Xia and W. Y. Wong, *Chinese Chemical Letters*, 2001, **18**, 629; (f) S. Cicchi, F. M. Cordero and D. Giomi, *Progress in Heterocycle Chemistry*, 2009, **21**, 308; (g) A. Bahy, Y. Kacem and B. B. Hassine, *Synth. Commun.*, 2010, **40**, 1377; (h) C. Gioia, F. Fini, A. Mazzanti, L. Bernardi and A. Ricci, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **131**, 9614.
- (a) P. Quadrelli, F. Lunghi, B. Bovio, W. Gautschi and P. Caramella, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.*, 2012, 1418; (b) E. C. Davison, M. E. Fox, A. B. Holmes, S. D. Roughley, C. J. Smith, G. M. Williams, J. E. Davies, P. R. Raitby, J. P. Adams, I. T. Forbes, N. J. Press and M. J. Thompson, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 2002, 1494; (c) A. Padwa and S. K. Bur, *Tetrahedron*, 2007, **63**, 5341; (d) T. Ueda, M. Inada, I. Okamoto, N. Morita and O. Tamura, *Org. Lett.*, 2008, **10**, 2043; (e) A. Brandi, F. Cardona, S. Cicchi, F. M. Cordero and A. Goti, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2009, **15**, 7808; (f) N. G. Argyropoulos, P. Gkizis and E. Coutouli-Argyropoulou, *Tetrahedron*, 2008, **64**, 8752.
- (a) J. M. Macdonald, H. T. Horsley, J. H. Ryan, S. Saubern and A. B. Holmes, *Org. Lett.*, 2008, **10**, 4227; (b) A. C. Flick and A. Padwa, *Arkivoc*, 2011, 137; (c) C. Frauenfelder, G. A. Schmid, T. Vogelsang and H.-J. Borschberg, *Chimia*, 2001, **55**, 828; (d) V. Nair and T. D. Suja, *Tetrahedron*, 2007, **63**, 12247; (e) F. M. Cordero, M. Gensini, A. Goti and A. Brandi, *Org. Lett.*, 2000, **2**, 2475; (f) A. Padwa, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2009, **74**, 6421; (g) S. Weinreb, *Chem. Rev.*, 2006, **106**, 2531; (h) A. I. Franklin, D. Bensa, H. Adams and I. Coldham, *Org. Biomol. Chem.*, 2011, **9**, 1901; (i) L. Fisera, *Top. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 2007, **7**, 287; (j) K. Harju, Yli-Kauhaluoma, *J. Mol. Diver.*, 2005, **9**, 187; (k) N. Arumugam, R. Raghunathan, V. Shammugaiah and N. Mathivanan, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2010, **20**, 3698; (l)

- T. K. M. Shing, A. W. F. Wong, T. Ikeno and T. Yamada, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2006, **71**, 3253; (m) M. Dai, Z. Wang and S. J. Danishefsky, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2008, **49**, 6613; (n) F. M. Cordero, F. De Sarlo and A. Brandi, *Monatsh. Chem.*, 2004, **135**, 649; (o) Z. Wang, K. Kaneda, Z. Fang and S. F. Martin, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2012, **53**, 477; (p) J. H. Jeong and S. M. Weinreb, *Org. Lett.*, 2006, **8**, 2309; (q) E. Coutouli-Argyropoulou, C. Xatzis and N. Argyropoulos, *Nucleosides, Nucleotides and Nucleic Acids*, 2008, **27**, 84.
7. (a) M. Potowski, M. Schürmann, H. Preut, A. P. Antonchick and H. Waldmann, *Nature Chemical Biology*, 2012, **8**, 428; (b) S. T. Abu-Orabi, M. Saleh, L. Al-Momani, I. Jibril and Y. Yousef, *Jordan J. Chem.*, 2006, **1**, 109; (c) F. Dumitraşcu, M. R. Caira, C. M. Drăghici, T. Căproiu, L. Barbu and D. G. Dumitrescu, *Arkivoc*, 2010, 97; (d) S. Muthusamy, S. A. Babu, C. Gunanathan, E. Suresh, P. Dastidar and R. V. Jasra, *Tetrahedron*, 2001, **57**, 7009; (e) T. Eehard, G. Ehrlich and P. Metz, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2011, **50**, 3892; (f) Y. Hashimoto, A. Takada, H. Takikawa and K. Suzuki, *Org. Biomol. Chem.*, 2012, **10**, 6003.
8. (a) X. Li, X. Yu and Y. Feng, *Chinese J. Chem.*, 2009, **27**, 1531; (b) A. S. Girgis, F. F. Barsoum and A. Samir, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2009, **44**, 2447; (c) A. S. Girgis, A. Ibrahim, N. Mishriky, J. N. Lisgarten, B. S. Potter and R. A. Palmer, *Tetrahedron*, 2001, **57**, 2015; (d) X. Li, A. Zheng, B. Liu, X. Yu and P. Yi, *J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 2010, **47**, 1157; (e) L. Gouiaa, N. Boukamcha, M. T. Martin and A. Khemiss, *Heterocyclic Commun.*, 2004, **10**, 227; (f) J. Jayasankaran, R. R. S. Manian, R. Venkatesan and R. Raghunathan, *Tetrahedron*, 2005, **61**, 5595; (g) A. Amal Raj and R. Raghunathan, *Tetrahedron*, 2001, **57**, 10293; (h) M. Poornachandran and R. Raghunathan, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2010, **49**, 127; (i) R. R. Kumar, S. Perumal, S. C. Manju, P. Bhatt, P. Yogeeswari and D. Sriram, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2009, **19**, 3461; (j) A. Amal Raj and R. Raghunathan, *Synth. Commun.*, 2002, **32**, 3295; (k) A. S. El-Ahl, *Heteroatom Chemistry*, 2002, **13**, 324.
9. (a) N. Boukamcha, R. Gharbi, M. T. Martin, A. Chiaroni, Z. Mighri and A. Khemiss, *Tetrahedron*, 1999, **55**, 449; (b) N. Paul, S. Kaladevi and S. Muthusubramanian, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 2012, **95**, 173.
10. P. K. Biswas, D. Bandyopadhyay, T. Prange, A. Neuman and A. Banerji, *Synth. Commun.*, 2011, **8**, 1146.
11. S. Chackalamannil and Y. Wang, *Tetrahedron*, 1997, **53**, 11203.
12. V. Sharma, R. Kalia, T. Raj, V. Gupta, N. Suri, A. K. Saxena, D. Sharma, S. S. Bhella, G. Singh and M. P. S. Ishar, *Acta Pharmaceutica Sinica B*, 2012, **2**, 32.
13. S. Basu, A. Ghosh and B. Hazra, *Phytotherapy Research*, 2005, **19**, 888.
14. T. Mosmann, *J. Immunol. Methods*, 1983, **65**, 55.

